

REPORT ON LCA AND SOCIAL-LCA OF THE SELECTED FOOD PRODUCTS

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REPORT
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VALUMICS - UNDERSTANDING FOOD VALUE
CHAINS AND NETWORK DYNAMICS

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Food Systems Dynamics

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ABOUT

VALUMICS stands for value chain dynamics and is a research project funded by the EU H2020 programme. VALUMICS will enable decision makers to evaluate policy impact on food value chains

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CONTENTS

List of figures	4
List of tables	4
List of abbreviations	5
SUMMARY	6
Goals	6
Methods	7
Main outcomes	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
2. METHODOLOGY	10
2.1 General rules for LCAs of food supply chains	12
2.2 Social LCA	13
2.3 Consumer market selection in food supply chains	15
3. CASE STUDIES	16
3.1 Salmon case study	16
3.1.1 Feed production	17
3.1.2 Juvenile and grow-out phase	18
3.1.3 Salmon processing.....	19
3.1.4 Distribution and consumption.....	20
3.1.5 Results and hotspot analysis	21
3.2 Butter case study	24
3.2.1 Feed and fertilizer production.....	25
3.2.2 On-farm milk production.....	26
3.2.3 Processing in dairy factory.....	26
3.2.4 Distribution and consumption.....	27
3.2.5 Results and hotspot analysis	28
3.3 Beef steak case study	31
3.3.1 Feed and fertilizer production.....	32
3.3.2 On-farm cattle production.....	33
3.3.3 Processing in beef factory.....	33
3.3.4 Distribution and consumption.....	34
3.3.5 Results and hotspot analysis	35
4. DISCUSSION.....	38
4.1 Hotspot analysis	38
4.2 Future scenarios for food supply chains	43
5. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	46
6. REFERENCES	47
7. ANNEXES	53

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1	Four steps of life cycle assessment.....	10
Figure 2.2	Example of comprehensive LCA model for agri-food system with 'cradle to grave'	12
Figure 2.3	Graph showing the social LCA indicators in the order of ranking against a normalised scale	15
Figure 3.1.1	System boundary of salmon supply chain	17
Figure 3.1.2	Distribution systems for Norwegian salmon supply chain	21
Figure 3.1.3	Impact contribution for salmon supply chain in Norway	22
Figure 3.1.4	Impact contribution for salmon supply chain to Denmark.....	23
Figure 3.1.5	Impact contribution for salmon supply chain to China	23
Figure 3.2.1	System boundary of butter supply chain.....	25
Figure 3.2.2	Distribution systems for Irish butter supply chain	27
Figure 3.2.3	Impact contribution for butter supply chain in Ireland	29
Figure 3.2.4	Impact contribution for butter supply chain to Germany.....	30
Figure 3.2.5	Impact contribution for butter supply chain to Japan	30
Figure 3.3.1	System boundary of beef supply chain.....	32
Figure 3.3.2	Distribution systems for Irish beef supply chain	34
Figure 3.3.3	Impact contribution for beef supply chain in Ireland	36
Figure 3.3.4	Impact contribution for beef supply chain to UK	36
Figure 3.3.5	Impact contribution for beef supply chain to USA.....	37
Figure 4.1.1	Impact contribution on salmon farm.....	40
Figure 4.1.2	Impact contribution on dairy farm	41
Figure 4.1.3	Impact contribution on beef farm	42

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1.1	Salmon waste at consumption stage	20
Table 3.2.1	Butter waste at consumption stage.....	28
Table 3.3.1	Beef waste at consumption stage	34

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EPS = Expanded polystyrene

GHG = greenhouse gas

GWP = Global warming potential

IPCC = Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

LCA = Life cycle assessment

LCI = Life cycle inventory

LCIA = life cycle impact assessment

LCWE = Life cycle working environment

UNEP-SETAC = United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC)

SUMMARY

This D4.4 LCA and Social-LCA report is the outcome of task 4.5. This task evaluates the environmental and social impacts of the selected food supply chain case studies in the VALUMICS project. The selected case studies focus on specific instances of salmon, beef and dairy supply chains. Life cycle assessment (LCA) was adopted as the evaluation tool in this task. It will use a holistic approach for system modelling of selected food supply chains. The chain will be defined in terms of raw materials (input) supply, primary production on farm, food processing, distribution and retail, and consumption stages. Moreover, descriptions of the selected case studies' food supply chains are included. In the LCA work, we defined a standard set of LCA rules for use across all studies (system boundary, functional unit, data quality, geographical specificity, calculation methods in the absence of observed data). For each case study, activity data has been taken from stakeholders in food supply chains or collated from secondary data sets. The environmental impact assessment covers all key impacts governed by EU legislation / policy such as: greenhouse gas emissions (European Climate Change Programme), freshwater eutrophication (Water and Nitrate Framework Directives), acidification (Air Quality Directive, Ammonia regulations). The social impacts will focus on worker stakeholder groups in UNEP-SETAC social LCA guidelines, with the consideration of data availability across the entire food supply chain. The interpretation of LCA focusses on identifying hotspots within the food supply chains. These hotspots are associated with different stakeholders at each stage in the chain. In order to improve the sustainability performance of selected food supply chains, recommendation and future scenarios are provided.

GOALS

The goal is to conduct the LCA and Social LCA for the selected case studies representing specific instances of selected food supply chains to identify the environmental and social hotspots. The objective is using life cycle analysis to model and identify areas to potentially improve the sustainability performance of these specific food supply chains in order to identify commonalities and differences by commodity, logistics and market.

METHODS

Life cycle assessment and social life cycle assessment was adopted for modeling the environmental and social impacts of case study food supply chains. Development of the model for different stages is based on available secondary data and the interviews with the stakeholders.

MAIN OUTCOMES

The LCA models identified on-farm production is the main hotspot within the selected food supply chains. The impact of transport process within food supply chain has a significant variation, which relates to the end market. Sea and road distribution system has very small contribution to environmental and social impact of food supply chain, however, the impact contribution of air transport is quite significant. Feed production and on-farm operations were identified as the most important activities to reduce the adverse impacts from primary production on farm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of VALUMICS project is using holistic systematic approach to enhance the resilience, integrity and sustainability of food value chains. To evaluate and improve the sustainability of food products, life cycle assessment (LCA) is the widely used method (ISO, 2006a). LCA can be used for identify the environmental (Hagelaar and van der Vorst, 2001) and social (Beske et al., 2014) hotspots in food supply chains, and providing strategic and operational advice on managemental strategies and agri-food policies. Environmental LCA and social LCA are adopted as key tools for sustainability evaluation in the overall project work. The LCA models are highly integrated and trans-disciplinary drawing on the expertise from different backgrounds. LCA models were developed for case studies, which were selected as representatives from different food sectors in the VALUMICS project.

WP4 focused on selected food systems and integrated value chain data from specific case studies with various secondary data to identify the critical points along the value chains. There have been many studies that consider hotspots for each sector (red meat, dairy, fish) using average data, some that have modelled the complete life cycle of each sector from cradle to grave, and very few that have attempted to model specific supply chains while trying to identify commonality and differences between raw materials (milk, red meat and fish). For this reason, the work focused on specific case studies (butter, salmon fillet and beef steak) for which data were industry sourced and sufficient to reliably model environmental and social impact indicators with similar quality data for the whole system. There are three case studies selected in WP4 for LCA evaluation: butter (representing dairy sector), salmon fillet (representing aquaculture sector) and beef steak (representing animal production sector). The Task4.5 will used environmental LCA and social LCA to estimate the environmental and social impacts associated with case studies. It will adopt a holistic approach based on life cycle assessment modelling.

Task 4.5 will define a standard set of rules (including system boundary, functional unit, data quality, geographical specificity, calculation methods in the absence of observed

data, etc.) for use across all case studies. The LCA models in VALUMICS case studies will collect and use activity data taken from specific spatial resources (as the identified country of origin in selected food supply chain cases) and representing processing unit (e.g. actual data from cooperative factories). The investigated environmental impact assessment will focus on key impacts governed by EU legislation / policy such as: greenhouse gas emissions (European Climate Change Programme), freshwater eutrophication (Water and Nitrate Framework Directives), acidification (Air Quality Directive, Ammonia regulations). The social impacts will focus on quantitative social indicators, such as working hours, health and safety, public living conditions, etc. (Chen and Holden, 2016).

This document is a deliverable for Task4.5 and presents the methodology for environmental LCA and social LCA, with the identified hotspots in selected food supply chains. The detailed description of LCA models for butter, salmon and beef steak will be presented. The identified environmental and social hotspots in these supply chains will be provided with recommendations.

2. METHODOLOGY

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a tool to assess the environmental impacts and resource consumptions throughout a product/process/service life cycle from raw material acquisition, via production / manufacture to use and ending with reuse or waste management (ISO, 2006a). It adopts a holistic approach from raw material extraction to waste disposal, which has a life cycle known as ‘cradle-to-grave’ (Klöpffer, 2003). LCA has been used for improving environmental performance (e.g. eco-design) (Knight and Jenkins, 2009) and to inform consumers about environmental impacts (Zackrisson et al., 2008), but there are far more possible uses (see Curran (2012)). There are four main steps in LCA: goal and scope, life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impacts assessment (LCIA) and interpretation.

Figure 2.1 Four steps of life cycle assessment

- *Goal and scope*: It provides a description of the product system in terms of the system boundaries and a functional unit (Rebitzer et al., 2004). The 'goal and scope' outlines what is the primary question that a LCA study intends to answer and how to answer. It serves as a core function in LCA and should be clearly defined in the early stage of LCA project.
- *LCI*: The function of LCI is compiling input (resource) and output (emission) from product over its life cycle in relation to the functional unit (Finnveden et al., 2009), which is the most time and labour intensive stage of LCA. In order to facilitate LCI and avoid duplication in compilation, public databases were developed at both national and regional scale. They can be used as background data and combined to foreground data, which is generated from modelled project to represent the characteristics of involved technique and management. The most widely used LCI databases for agricultural processes include the Eco-invent (Weidema et al., 2013), Agri-footprint (Braungart et al., 2007), Gabi database (Thinkstep, 2014). The temporal and spatial resolution could have a significant of the results of LCA (Wegener Sleeswijk, 2011). Therefore, a survey based LCI or regionalized LCI (Yang, 2016) may help improve the accuracy of LCA.
- *LCIA*: In LCIA stage, the magnitude and significance of the potential environmental impacts of the studied system is evaluated (ISO, 2006a). In LCIA, there are four mandatory steps ('selection and definition of impact categories', 'classification', 'characterization' and 'evaluating and reporting LCIA') and three optional steps ('normalization', 'grouping' and 'weighting') (Finnveden et al., 2009). Currently, there are many different LCIA methods available (e.g. IPCC, ReCiPe, CML, Impacts 2002+, TRACI, etc), and all methods cover some most concerned impact issues include climate change, acidification, eutrophication, etc. (Hauschild and Huijbregts, 2015). For agricultural and food systems, climate change is the most commonly considered impact method, usually calculated using IPCC or CML methods (Casey and Holden, 2005, Yan et al., 2011, Fantin et al., 2012) and expressed as carbon footprint (O'Brien et al., 2015).
- *Interpretation*: Interpretation is designed for evaluating the results from the previous phases in relation to the goal and scope. And relevant conclusions

and recommendations should be provided (ISO, 2006a). One of the most important issues in this stage is uncertainty analysis. It could lie in LCI database (Takano et al., 2014) or LCA software (Herrmann and Moltesen, 2014), therefore, it is need to make clear statement about the choice of database and software when comparative assessment is desired. In addition, normalization and weighting could also contribute to uncertainty of results (Finnveden et al., 2009).

2.1 GENERAL RULES FOR LCAs OF FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS

The system boundaries of LCA models in VALUMICS project adopted the 'cradle to grave' approach. It covers off-farm raw materials extraction, primary production on farm, post-harvest storage and distribution, processing at food factory, distribution and retail, consumption and final waste management (etc. recycle /reuse and disposal).

Figure 2.2 Example of comprehensive LCA model for agri-food system with 'cradle to grave'

The main processes of selected food supply chains can be grouped into 5 stages: agriculture inputs supply, primary production on farm, processing at factory, distribution and retail, and consumption. The data quality for each stage was defined as follow:

- Agriculture inputs supply: activity data for input materials was refined from national level data, and standard LCA database (e.g. Ecoinvent, Agri-footprint) was used as background data.
- Primary production on farm: data for national average farm was refined from central statistical office and used for modelling production on farm in specific food supply chain.
- Processing at factory: first hand data was collected from survey of representative processing facility in each food supply chain.
- Distribution and retail: representative markets for specific food chain were identified. Route based distribution data to representative markets were collected or estimated. Regional level data for energy consumption and waste generation in retail stage was estimated based on literature or communication.
- Consumption: consumption and waste generation data were estimated according to identified markets. Regional level data of energy consumption and waste generation in consumption stage has been estimated based on literature.

2.2 SOCIAL LCA

Comparing to environmental life cycle assessment, social life cycle assessment (Social LCA) is a new method, and there is no standard methodology for conducting the assessment. Although there is no standard method for social LCA study, social LCA guidelines from UNEP-SETAC is one of the most adopted method for social LCA and it can serve as a suitable framework for social LCA practice (Wu et al., 2014). There is no consensus in terms of impact categories. Two types of impact categories have been proposed:

- Type I aggregates results into groups according to a scoring system and stakeholder context.

- Type II impact categories are defined by causal relationships with midpoint and endpoint categories, which are similar to environmental LCA impact categories.

In this study, the social LCAs focus on the quantitative social impacts of the supply chain. Therefore, we selected the social indicators from Type II impact categories. The quantitative social data was mainly derived from life cycle working environment (LCWE) database in Gabi software. In addition, supplementary data was collected from literature to fill some data gaps in LCWE database. Field surveys were also conducted in production sites (e.g. processing facilities) to obtain the social information like working hours and male to female employee ratio. After analysing the availability of social data from whole supply chain perspective, the selected social indicators were working hours, fatal accident and non-fatal accident. The social LCA modelling followed the same method developed by Chen and Holden (2016).

For the salmon case study, a survey was conducted to identify and rank the most important social indicators in salmon industry. About 50 respondents from Norway completed the survey to rank the indicators in terms of how relevant they are to assess the social impacts of salmon aquaculture. A list of 15 indicators were chosen from the UNEP SETAC guidelines and included in the online survey. The indicators were focused on the stakeholder groups such as workers, employers, consumers and the local consumers. The respondents of the survey were mainly stakeholders from the Norwegian aquaculture sector including producers, market analysts, researchers and members of branch organizations. According to the survey results, the indicators related to the stakeholder group 'workers' were ranked highest and 'work related fatal and non-fatal accidents' was identified as the most important indicator for social LCA.

Figure 2.3 Graph showing the social LCA indicators in the order of ranking against a normalised scale.

2.3 CONSUMER MARKET SELECTION IN FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS

In order to reflect the impacts of transportation systems in different food supply chains, three types of distribution networks were designed for each case studies. The main difference in the distribution networks is the transportation approach from food processing facility to retailers in identified consumer markets. We assumed the food products will be transported mainly by three types of transportation: truck, ship and airplane. Accordingly, we identified three end markets: domestic market, European market and global market outside of Europe. Based on data availability (e.g. particular type of food waste at consumption stage) and the market share, a European market and a global market were chosen for each food supply chain. Therefore, in this study, nine food supply chains were identified.

3. CASE STUDIES

3.1 SALMON CASE STUDY

According to Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and World Bank, the global demand for food, especially the marine based protein is increasing. Salmon is an important commodity in global seafood market and about 70% of the world's salmon production is farmed. The main salmon production sites are located in Norway, Chile, Scotland and Canada (Marine Harvest, 2017). Due to the data availability and market share, the salmon supply chain with primary production in Norway was selected as representative of Atlantic salmon products.

Following the general rules above, the functional unit for LCA models of salmon supply chain is 1 kg of salmon, the system boundary is shown in Figure 3. The boxes without colour represent the processes, which use national level data or background data from standard LCA database (e.g. Eco-invent, Gabi database, Agri-footprint database) for LCA modelling. The blue boxes are the processes, which demand the survey data from a processing facility. The red boxes mainly refer to the waste information in distribution and consumption stages. The processes involving the different lice treatment methods used today in salmon farming are not considered in this LCA system due to lack of data availability. The processes involving cleaner fish farming and catch are also not included due to lack of data availability and considering the fact that the volume of cleaner fish used for biological lice treatment is significantly lower than the volume of salmon deployed in the net pens. Due to the primary data availability issue, the data for distribution and consumption stage is derived from literature review. The resolution of data requirement from the consumption stage is limited to fish category at national level. The main stages of salmon supply chain in LCA models are shown as follow:

- Feed production
- Juvenile production and grow-out phase
- Primary and secondary processing
- Distribution & consumption

Figure 3.1.1 System boundary of salmon supply chain

3.1.1 FEED PRODUCTION

Feed is the main part of primary production on salmon farm. The composition of salmon feed can be categorized into 5 ingredient types: marine oil, marine protein, vegetable oil, vegetable protein and supplements. The salmon feed has been identified as the hotspot of many environmental impacts in salmon supply chain (Ziegler et al., 2013, Ytrestøyl et al., 2015, Taelman et al., 2013). In order to improve the environmental performance of salmon supply chain, the composition of salmon feed has changed significantly in past decades.

From 1990 to 2012, the share of vegetable ingredients (protein and oil) increased from less than 10% to 67% (Norwegian Seafood Federation, 2013). Although this change reduced some environmental impacts, e.g. greenhouse gas emission, it shifted more environmental burdens to terrestrial ecosystems. In addition, vegetable feed has a positive effect on the FIFO (fish in – fish out) ratio, but it may have an effect on the nutrient content of the salmon. Nutrient balance accounting and resource budget (protein, fat, energy, phosphorous, n-3 fatty acids (EPA, DHA)) are methods that have been used to monitor the retention of nutrients in the farmed fish (Ytrestøyl et al., 2011). Optimizing the feed conversion ratio (FCR: kg feed used/kg fish produced) has been an important research topic in salmon industry.

To model the feed production, the national average data was refined from previous surveys and references. The marine and vegetable ingredients account around 31% and 66%, respectively. The remaining 3% is from supplements. The main components of LCA model for salmon feed are marine oil and protein, vegetable oil, protein and starch, and some micro ingredients. For marine component part, in addition to the main ingredients (e.g. anchoveta, herring, soybean), the other ingredients (e.g. Sprat, Capelin, wheat gluten, etc.) with minor share of feed composite were also modelled in sub-model of feed. The country of origin for these ingredients has a global scope, including South America, Asia and Europe.

3.1.2 JUVENILE AND GROW-OUT PHASE

The primary salmon farming has two main stages: the juvenile stage (smolt production) in freshwater in a land-based hatchery and grow out stage in sea cages. The total freshwater production cycle takes approximately 10-16 months and the total seawater production cycle take approximately 14-24 months, hence a total cycle length of 24-40 months (Marine Harvest, 2017). A suitable feed strategy not only influences the operation cost and productivity, but also has a significant impact on environmental performance (e.g. climate change, eutrophication) of salmon farming stage. Governmental monitoring and legal requirements ensure that aquaculture farms report occurrences of sea lice, escapees, the use of medication and water quality and sediment monitoring in the areas close to the farms. There is an increasing awareness

that monitoring data should be accessible in the public domain to enhance the transparency and help building an image of responsibility for the sector.

Compared to feed component, the juvenile and grow-out production phase is more straightforward. Except the salmon feed, the main inputs for this stage is energy (electricity and diesel) and chemical consumption at the production plant. The material for aquaculture equipment, maintenance and packaging was also included. The waste management scenario (e.g. recycling) for the inputs material was applied and the ratio was based on LCA report by Nofir (<https://nofir.no/lca/>). Mass allocation was adopted to allocate the impacts between salmon products and dead salmon.

3.1.3 SALMON PROCESSING

The processing data for LCA modelling was taken from a salmon processing plant in the western part of Norway. The main product of the processing plant is whole gutted salmon. The by-products and residue from this facility include blood and guts. The ratio of main product (82%), by-product (10%) and residue (3%), and weight loss (5%) as a result of starvation before slaughter was taken from an internal report of EU FP7 project SENSE (Ingolfsdottir et al., 2013). The main inputs of salmon processing unit are electricity for processing machine, detergent and disinfectant for washing and cleaning, and packaging material. All the input data was derived from factory survey. All the chemicals for washing and cleaning were grouped into three categories for LCA modelling. Alkylbenzene sulfonate was used as detergent. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) was assumed to represent disinfectant. The remaining cleaning chemicals were assumed to be soap. Synthetic rubber was used as the main material for disposable cap and gloves.

The main materials for packaging include EPS box, corrugated board box and aluminium and plastic film. Mass allocation is adopted to allocate the impacts between main product (salmon for human consumption) and by-product (guts for marine feed). According to Ziegler et al. (2013), different weighting factor was adopted for food and feed part. The food weighting factor of food is 1 and weighting factor of feed is 0.5. The allocation factor was calculated based on the weighting factor for food and feed as follow:

$$\text{Allocation factor for feed} = 0.5 * (\text{Mass}_{\text{feed}} / (\text{Mass}_{\text{feed}} + \text{Mass}_{\text{food}}))$$

$$\text{Allocation factor for food} = 1 - \text{Allocation feed}$$

3.1.4 DISTRIBUTION AND CONSUMPTION

In order to reflect the effect of different transportation networks on entire food supply chains, domestic, European and International markets were identified. The main criteria of choosing an end market was availability of consumption data. Since the LCA model includes consumption stage, the waste generation from end consumer could influence the total impact in a significant way. Based on the available data, the resolution of food waste at consumption is fish category at specific countries. Depending on the secondary data availability for different countries, the main market for Norwegian salmon was selected. In order to avoid the duplication, the end markets for all three case studies we selected.

In the salmon case, the identified domestic, European and International markets are Norway, Denmark and China respectively. The salmon waste from consumption stage for all end markets were shown in Table 3.1.1. For the food waste at retail stage and in supermarkets, this study adopted the average value for fish waste in supermarket (5%) (Xue et al., 2017).

Table 3.1.1 Salmon waste at consumption stage

End market location	Waste from consumption	Reference
Norway	7%	Gjerris and Gaiani (2013) & Xue et al. (2017)
Denmark	7%	Xue et al. (2017)
China	7%	Song et al. (2015)

The suitable distribution networks for Norwegian salmon to each end market were shown in Figure 3.1.2. The distance of road transport was estimated from Google Maps, the distance on sea and air transport was estimated from Port website (<http://ports.com/>) and Distance website (<https://www.distance.to/>), respectively.

Figure 3.1.2 Distribution systems for Norwegian salmon supply chain

3.1.5 RESULTS AND HOTSPOT ANALYSIS

The environmental and social impacts of the main stages in Norwegian salmon supply chain are shown in ANNEXES 1-3. Based on the results, the salmon supply chain to China has biggest total values for most of environmental and social indicators, which were influenced by air transport in a significant way. Comparing the salmon supply chain with other distribution networks, the impact contribution of air transport can greatly increase the value of fossil fuel based abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, photochemical oxidation and acidification. ANNEX 4 shows the share of GHG emissions in Norwegian salmon supply chain to China. The aviation fuel accounts more than 69% of total GHG emissions from cradle to retailer gate.

Comparing the environmental performance of salmon supply chains in Norway and Denmark, the results suggested most of the environmental impacts in Norway are more significant than the impacts in Denmark. The on-road transport (truck) is responsible for the greater environmental impacts in domestic salmon supply chain. Although the transport distance to Denmark is longer, the lower environmental impacts per functional unit in sea transport reduced the total adverse effect of distribution network.

For the social impacts, the values of all three indicators did not have significant variation in each distribution network. The working hours, fatal accident and non-fatal accident in air transport have the greatest value. Although the air traffic is fastest and safest transport approach, the transport capacity of plane is limited, especially

compared to the container ships. In this LCA model, the social information was derived from life cycle working environment (LCWE) database in Gabi software. The capacity of container ship and aircraft in LCWE database is 27500 ton and 65 ton, respectively. The greater transport capacity of ship significantly reduced the working time and accident rate per ton of product transported per kilometre. All three social indicators in sea transport distribution network have the lowest impact value.

The Figures 3.1.3- 3.1.5 show the impact contribution from main stages of each food supply chain. The three figures suggest that the main impacts of salmon supply chain are from aquaculture production of which feed production is the biggest contributor. In domestic and Danish supply chains, the live salmon production on farm accounts for 80%-88% of total environmental and social impacts. This suggests managing the environmental and social impacts of aquaculture is critical for sustainability of salmon supply chains. For the supply chains in Norway and Denmark, the impact contribution from each main supply chain stage has a similar pattern. In the supply chain to China, the impact contribution of aquaculture stage has a wide variation. It has lowest impact contribution on abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) (16%) and highest impact contribution on terrestrial ecotoxicity and fatal injuries (87%).

Figure 3.1.3 Impact contribution for salmon supply chain in Norway

Figure 3.1.4 Impact contribution for salmon supply chain to Denmark

Figure 3.1.5 Impact contribution for salmon supply chain to China

In the salmon supply chain to China, the air transport system has significant environmental impacts on many indicators (e.g. abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), global

warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, fresh water and marine aquatic ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation and acidification, non-fatal injury). For social indicators, air transport also increased the distribution stage associated impact contribution on indicators of working time and non-fatal injuries. Compared to the road and sea distribution networks, airfreight distribution system has a lower transport capacity, which leads to the increase of social impacts.

3.2 BUTTER CASE STUDY

Butter is one of the most important commodities in the dairy sector. Compared to yoghurt, cream and milk, it has greater possibility to be traded globally. The world demand for butter keeps increasing, especially from Asia (Buzby, 2001). Similar to other food products, organic or naturally produced butter is becoming more favourable in various markets (Sahota, 2006). A grass based dairy system can not only meet this demand, but also has the potential to improve the sustainability by reducing the environmental impacts of dairy supply chain (O'Brien et al., 2014). The Irish dairy industry is a typical example of grass based grazing system (Fitzgerald et al., 2009). Therefore, the Irish butter supply chain was selected as the case study for dairy sector in VALUMICS project.

The functional unit for butter LCA models is 1 kg of butter. The system boundary for the butter supply chain is shown in Figure 3.2.1. The boxes without colour use national level data or background data from standard LCA database. The data for farm inputs were taken from Chen and Holden (2018a) and the characteristics of national average dairy farm were modelled, which was based on the data from national farm survey (Hennessy and Moran, 2015). The blue boxes are the processes, which demand the survey data from a processing facility. The processing data for butter production was taken from one of the Aurivo processing factories in Ireland. The red boxes are waste information in distribution and consumption stages, which was based on literature review. The main stages of butter supply chain in LCA models are shown as follow:

- Feed and fertilizer production
- On-farm milk production
- Processing in dairy factory

- Distribution & consumption

Figure 3.2.1 System boundary of butter supply chain

3.2.1 FEED AND FERTILIZER PRODUCTION

The Irish dairy farm is grass grazing based system. The majority of feed for cattle is derived from grass, with complementary feed of silage and concentrate feed. The composition of concentrate feed was taken from Chen and Holden (2018a). It represents the concentrate feed used in average Irish dairy farm. The concentrate feed is the mix of two concentrate feed with crude protein at 16% and 20%. The ratio for the two concentrate is 1:1. The main components for concentrate are maize grain, barley grain, rape meal, palm oil, palm kernel meal, soybean meal, distiller' dried grain, lime,

wheat grain, citrus pulp and sunflower meal. The country of origin for the ingredients are mainly located in Europe, America and Asia. The N, P, K fertilizer is another main input for dairy farm. The fertilizer application for dairy farm follow the Teagasc report and recommendations (O'Donoghue et al., 2015)

3.2.2 ON-FARM MILK PRODUCTION

The on-farm milk production was identified as the main stage for environmental impacts of dairy supply chain (Flysjö et al., 2014). For example, the enteric fermentation of dairy cows can account more than 45% of total GHG emission of milk production (Chen and Holden, 2018b). In the VALUMICS model, we included all the on-farm processes with high emission: enteric fermentation, manure storage, animal excretion on field, fertilizer and slurry application, nitrate leaching (See ANNEX 5). The impacts of on-farm material consumption (e.g. plastics, cleaning chemicals and pesticide) were also included. To allocate the environmental impacts between milk and co-product meat, allocation was applied based on energy and protein requirements of the herd (O'Brien et al., 2012). The proportion of total energy and protein requirement of the herd used to produce meat in the Irish grass-based system is 12%, which was originally calculated using the Moorepark Dairy System Model (Shalloo et al., 2004).

3.2.3 PROCESSING IN DAIRY FACTORY

The processing data was taken from a butter processing facility in County Roscommon, Ireland. The main by-products in butter production are butter milk and skim milk. The output of the by-products and loss at processing was obtained from factory survey. The main inputs of butter processing unit are energy (electricity for equipment and thermal energy from boiler), chemical for washing and cleaning, and packaging material. Except the energy consumption, all inputs were derived from factory survey. Due to the specification of energy recording system in collaborative factory, data that differentiates the energy consumption of butter production-line from other production lines was not obtained. Therefore, the average energy consumption of Irish butter processing was used (Finnegan et al., 2017). The GHG emission factor for the thermal energy generation was obtained from emission report by sustainable energy authority

of Ireland (SEAI, 2018). The allocation factor between butter and by-products (including waste and loss during production) was derived from Feitz et al. (2005). The main process from cradle to butter processing gate is shown in ANNEX 5.

3.2.4 DISTRIBUTION AND CONSUMPTION

Based on the location of butter processing facility and the Bord Bia market report (Bord Bia, 2018), three end markets, i.e Ireland, Germany and Japan were identified for Irish butter supply chains. By communication with stakeholders of Irish butter industry and managers of butter facility in this case study, three suitable distribution networks for Irish butter supply chains were identified as shown in Figure 3.2.2. The distance of on road transport was estimated from Google Map, the distance on sea and air transport was estimated from Port website (<http://ports.com/>) and Distance website (<https://www.distance.to/>), respectively.

Figure 3.2.2 Distribution systems for Irish butter supply chain

For each end market, the butter waste from consumption was identified from literature and UK WRAP website (<http://www.wrap.org.uk/>). The ratios of wasted butter for all end markets were shown in Table 3.2.1. Regarding the food waste at retail and at supermarkets, it was assumed that around 0.5% of butter in supermarket would be wasted (Scholz et al., 2015).

Table 3.2.1 Butter waste at consumption stage

End market location	Waste from consumption	Reference
Ireland	10%	WRAP (2011)
Germany	8%	Xue et al. (2017)
Japan	1%	Parry (2015)

3.2.5 RESULTS AND HOTSPOT ANALYSIS

The environmental and social impacts of main stages in butter supply chains are shown in ANNEXES 6-8. Based on the results, the butter supply chain to Japan has biggest total values for most of the environmental and social indicators. It suggests that air transport can lead to significant impacts on some environmental and social issues, especially on abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity and acidification. ANNEX 9 shows the share of GHG emissions in butter supply chain to Japan. The aviation accounts for an important share of total GHG emissions. The main contribution comes from CO₂ emissions from aircraft engine, which depends on the transport distance and the CO₂ emissions intensity of aviation fuel.

For the total social impacts, the butter supply chain to Japan has the biggest value in working time and non-fatal injuries and lowest value in fatal injuries. The low butter waste at consumption stage reduces the social impacts in this global butter supply chain. The transport distance and much greater transport capacity of container ship leads to the lower value of working time and non-fatal injuries in supply chain to Germany.

The distribution network could have significant environmental impacts on global food supply chain when an aircraft is used for transportation. However, for the butter supply chain, the raw milk production is the main environmental and social hotspot in domestic, European and global market (see Figures 3.2.3- 3.2.5). For domestic market, raw milk production on farm accounts for 70%-90% environmental and social impacts of butter supply chain. For the German market, the results show a similar trend. However, the reduction of share was noticed on environmental indicators of

abiotic depletion, abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), global warming (GWP100a), ozone layer depletion (ODP), human toxicity, freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity. The raw milk production related impacts increased for the rest of the environmental indicators, which was mainly driven by the more complex distribution network (ship + truck). For social indicators, the contribution of raw milk production has higher share on working time, non-fatal injuries, fatal injuries. The main reason is that the lower food waste at consumer stage reduces the total social impact of butter supply chain to Germany.

Figure 3.2.3 Impact contribution for butter supply chain in Ireland

For the global supply chain, although air transportation may have a significant contribution to some environmental impacts, the raw milk production on farm still accounts for a dominating share in many environmental impacts and all social indicators. Managing the environmental and social impacts of raw milk production on farm is critical for sustainability of all butter supply chains.

Figure 3.2.4 Impact contribution for butter supply chain to Germany

Figure 3.2.5 Impact contribution for butter supply chain to Japan

In this study, it was found that to be able to produce 1 kg butter, it requires almost 8 kg of raw milk as main inputs. This is the main reason that raw milk production is the impact hotspot in entire butter supply chain.

3.3 BEEF STEAK CASE STUDY

As one of the main meat categories, the beef supply chain is very important for global food security. The increasing of beef consumption is observed as a global trend (McAlpine et al., 2009). This increase may further intensify the significant environmental impacts (FAO, 2013) and social impacts (Gadd, 2012) of beef supply chain. Therefore, managing the sustainability of beef supply chain is critical. Due to the data availability, the Irish beef supply chain was selected as the case study for meat sector in VALUMICS projects.

The functional unit for beef LCA models is 1 kg of beef steak. The system boundary for beef supply chain is shown in Figure 3.3.1. The boxes without colour use national level data or background data from standard LCA database. For the farm inputs and primary production stages, the national average data was derived the beef profitability technologies report from Teagasc (2016) and Irish national farm survey (Dillon et al., 2017). The blue boxes are the processes, which demand the survey data from processing facility. The processing data for butter production was taken from one of the one beef processing factory located in county Cork, Ireland. The red boxes are waste information in distribution and consumption stages, which was based on literature review. The main stages of beef supply chain in LCA models are shown as follow:

- Feed and fertilizer production
- On-farm cattle production
- Processing in beef factory
- Distribution & consumption

Figure 3.3.1 System boundary of beef supply chain

3.3.1 FEED AND FERTILIZER PRODUCTION

Similar to the dairy farm, the main diet for cattle in specialized Irish beef farm is grass. Silage is normally fed to the weanlings when they are housed or fed to animals during winter. When further feed is demand, concentrate will be used for any cattle. The ratio for grass, silage and concentrate is taken from Sharma et al. (2018). The LCA model was developed for concentrate with crude protein content at 16%. The average P and K index for soil in beef farm was assumed to be 2 (<https://www.teagasc.ie/crops/soil--soil-fertility/grassland/beef/>), and the N, P, K fertilizer application follows the Teagasc fertilizer advice (<https://www.teagasc.ie/news--events/news/2016/soil-fertility->

[trends.php](#)). The background LCA data for feed and fertilizer was derived from Agri-footprint and Ecoinvent database.

3.3.2 ON-FARM CATTLE PRODUCTION

According to national farm survey, the average land area for beef farm is 40 acres. The livestock unit is 51 with stocking rate around 1.3. The most common system operated with 20 cows producing calves for replacements and beef consumption. It was assumed that these calves are weaned at approximately 184 days (Casey and Holden, 2006). The average live weight per hectare per year is 297kg. Similar to the dairy supply chain, the main environmental hotspot of beef supply chain is also from cattle raising at farm (Foley et al., 2011). The main processes with highest emission are enteric fermentation, manure storage, animal excretion on field, fertilizer and slurry application, nitrate leaching (See ANNEX 10). The impacts of on-farm material consumption (e.g. plastics, cleaning chemicals and pesticide) are also included.

3.3.3 PROCESSING IN BEEF FACTORY

The processing data for LCA modelling was taken from a beef processing plant in county Cork, Ireland. The main product of the processing plant is beef. The by-products from this beef processing facility include offal, blood, bone, fat, hide and other bio-waste. The main inputs of beef processing facility are electricity, water, thermal energy and packaging material. All the input data was obtained from the processing plant survey. Soap and alkylbenzene sulfonate were used as the main detergents. Synthetic rubber was used as the main material for disposable cap and gloves. The main materials for packaging include corrugated board box and aluminium and plastic film. According to discussions with the red meat industry actors, biophysical allocation is a preferred allocation approach. The allocation factors were calculated based on the energy requirements for animal physiological functions of growth, milk production, reproduction, activity and maintenance (FAO LEAP. , 2016). The detailed calculation for allocation factor can be found in Chen et al. (2017).

3.3.4 DISTRIBUTION AND CONSUMPTION

Identifying the end markets for consumer follows the same criteria in previous case studies. Three end markets were identified for Irish beef supply chains, with the consideration of the location of beef processing facility and the Bord Bia market report (Bord Bia, 2018). The domestic, European and international markets are located in Ireland, UK and USA. By communication with stakeholders of Irish beef industry and managers of beef facility in this case study, we identified three suitable distribution networks for Irish beef supply chains as shown in Figure 3.3.2. The distance of on road transport was estimated from Google Map, the distance on sea and air transport was estimated from Port website (<http://ports.com/>) and Distance website (<https://www.distance.to/>), respectively.

Figure 3.3.2 Distribution systems for Irish beef supply chain

The beef waste from consumption stage for all end markets is shown in Table 3.3.1. For the food waste at retailer and in supermarkets, this study adopted the average value for beef waste in supermarket (2.5%) (Scholz et al., 2015)

Table 3.3.1 Beef waste at consumption stage

End market location	Waste from consumption	Reference
Ireland	6%	WRAP (2011)
UK	6%	WRAP (2011)
USA	13%	(Venkat, 2011)

3.3.5 RESULTS AND HOTSPOT ANALYSIS

The environmental and social impacts of main stages in Irish beef supply chains are shown in ANNEXES 11-13. Based on the results, the beef supply chain to USA has biggest total values for most of environmental and social indicators. In contrast to air transport in previous case studies, the air transport in beef supply chain has lower contribution in total impact, especially in indicator of climate change (GHG emission). There are two reasons for this lower share of impact. First, the GHG emission of beef production is much higher the GHG emission of other food production. Second, the transport distance from processing facility to end market is much shorter than the transport distance in other food supply chains. In ANNEX 14, the impact share of air transport accounts less than 24% of total GHG emission from cradle to retailer gate. For the other environmental indicators, the air transport still has significant influence on fossil fuel based abiotic depletion, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, photochemical oxidation and acidification. The results suggested the environmental and social impacts of beef supply chains in Ireland are smaller than the corresponding impacts in beef supply chain to UK. This is mainly due to the shorter transport distance. For the social impacts, the results are very similar to the findings in the previous case studies. The variation of social indicators is not very significant in each distribution network. The air transport supply chain has the greatest value in all social indicators. Figures 3.3.3- 3.3.5 show the impact contribution from main stages of each food supply chain. Similar to the salmon and butter supply chains, the figures also suggested the main impacts are from primary production on farm. In domestic and UK supply chains, the beef production on farm account for 85%-92% of total environmental and social impacts. In the beef supply chain to USA, the impact contribution of primary production stage has a wide variation. It has lowest impact contribution on human toxicity (26%) and highest impact contribution on terrestrial ecotoxicity (83%). In addition, due to the high food waste at consumer stage, the impact contribution of consumption in Irish beef supply chain to USA could also be significant. Managing the consumer waste in beef supply chain will have an important influence on overall environmental and social impact of beef supply chain.

Figure 3.2.3 Impact contribution for beef supply chain in Ireland

Figure 3.2.4 Impact contribution for Irish beef supply chain to UK

Figure 3.2.5 Impact contribution for Irish beef supply chain to USA

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 HOTSPOT ANALYSIS

Based on the results of each case study presented in this report, two general conclusions can be drawn. First, the market and thus the transport system has potential to significantly influence the environmental and social impacts of food supply chains. The transport distance and approach are the key factors to total impacts. Air transport is a critical part of the global supply chain as it can bridge the global demand and supply in an efficient way. This rapid distribution network is very important to food commodity, since they normally have a short shelf-life. However, air transport leads to impacts, especially on environmental aspect. In order to minimize the impacts of long-distance transport, other transport approaches (e.g. sea transport) can be adopted. However, sea transport takes longer time to deliver food and would require a freezing process, which would affect the economic characteristic (e.g. selling price) and relevant consumer preferences. Therefore, air transport is the only viable approach for some food supply chains, which have high demand of freshness. The best possible method to lower the environmental impacts of air transport would be sustainable aviation fuel since the main contribution of environmental impacts comes from the production and consumption of conventional aviation fuel. The conventional aviation fuel is derived from fossil fuel, therefore, replacing conventional aviation fuel with sustainable aviation fuel offers a great chance to reduce the air transport associated environmental impacts (Pierobon et al., 2018).

In addition to air transport, the primary production on farm stage was identified as the common hotspot in all the selected food supply chains. The management of environmental and social impacts of on-farm production is critical to overall sustainability performance of food supply chains. In order to identify the sustainability hotspots of on-farm production, contribution analysis was performed. Figures 3.4.1-3.4.3 show the contribution of main stages in on-farm production. In salmon farm, the feed production accounts for a dominating part in almost all environmental indicators, except marine aquatic ecotoxicity and eutrophication. In beef and dairy farms, feed production is the main contributor to terrestrial ecotoxicity. Feed production also has

significant share in the impact of freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity in both farms. And the effect of feed in dairy farm is more notable. In contrast, the influence of feed on eutrophication in beef farm is more than the effect in dairy farm. In dairy farm, the eutrophication is mainly caused by fertilizer. The reason is that dairy farms use more fertilizer to grow the on-farm grass as silage feed. In addition, feed production also leads to a notable share in environmental impacts of abiotic depletion (both fossil fuel and non-fossil fuel), global warming, ozone depletion, human toxicity marine aquatic ecotoxicity, acidification. For non-fatal injury, the contribution of feed production in beef farm is more significant. This is due to the more off-farm feed consumption in beef farms.

In salmon farm, the on-farm emission dominated the impact of marine aquatic ecotoxicity, eutrophication, working hours, non-fatal injury and fatal injury. The smolt production had big contribution on some impacts, especially on abiotic depletion (9.3%), photochemical oxidation (6.3%) and non-fatal injury (17%). The energy consumption and transport process at farming stage had very small contribution to all indicators. The most important contributions are for biotic depletion (fossil fuels) and acidification, which account 4%-6% of total impact.

Based on the results from the salmon farm, the salmon feed production is the key hotspot of most of the environmental impacts. Some feed ingredients (e.g. soy protein) have significant environmental impacts, therefore, replacing them with some low impact ingredients can significantly the sustainability performance of salmon (Rustad, 2016). Currently, the most popular innovative ingredients for salmon feed are insect meal (Popoff et al., 2017, Belghit et al., 2018) and single cell protein from microalgae (Sørensen et al., 2016, Kiron et al., 2012). Although these alternatives can potentially improve the sustainability of salmon feed, the production of these ingredients needs to be optimised and some challenges still need to be solved before commercial application. Currently, the alternative ingredients cost more than conventional ingredients. A better food and safety regulation for the use of these alternatives in salmon feed needs to be developed. In addition, the productivity needs to be improved to reduce the production cost (Govaerts, 2018). The public acceptance could be another issue for further development of alternative salmon feed (Popoff et al., 2017).

The main social hotspot is on-farm operation. Health and safety issues are mainly caused by musculoskeletal problems and occupational accidents, which can lead to work-related sick leave and health worries. However, the salmon industry is having a trend for automation of maintenance and operation activities, such as automated feed refilling and monitoring cameras to reduce the need of labour on the farms (EXPOSED, 2017). These automated operations can reduce work related risks to health and safety of the workers. Salmon feed and on-farm operation together account for more than 90% of total impacts for all indicators.

Figure 4.1.1 Impact contribution on salmon farm

In the dairy and beef farms, on-farm emissions had significant share in global warming, photochemical oxidation, working hours and fatal injury. The water supply has more significant influence on working hours and non- fatal injury in the dairy farm compared to the beef farm. Fertilizer production was also responsible for a big share in many environmental impacts, especially abiotic depletion (fossil fuels & non- fossil fuels), human toxicity and marine aquatic ecotoxicity. The impact contribution of fertilizer in dairy farm is more significant than the impact in beef farm. This suggested that more

fertilizer was used for on-farm silage production. The greater fertilizer application also demands more energy input for on-farm practise, for example the diesel consumption for fertilizer spreading. Therefore, the energy consumption in dairy farm had a bigger share in impact contribution. The main impact of energy consumption is for indicator of abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) and ozone layer depletion. The transport in dairy farm took a very small share in all impact indicators, however, the impact contribution of transport in beef farm was more significant. The higher contribution of transport in beef farm is mainly caused by the greater amount of off-farm feed. The manure management in dairy and beef farm had very significant contribution in acidification (56%-63%), eutrophication (34%-44%) and global warming (13%-18%). The main emission for these impacts includes NH₃ and nitrate leaching from manure storage and field excretion. Similar findings were identified in previous studies (Chen and Holden, 2018a, Yan et al., 2013b, O'Brien et al., 2012).

Figure 4.1.2 Impact contribution on dairy farm

Figure 4.1.3 Impact contribution on beef farm

For dairy and beef farms, different processes in farm production can influence different impact indicators in a significant way. Improving the safety measures in farming practise can greatly reduce fatal accidents in both farms. Using automatic farming system would reduce the working time, therefore it can increase the production efficiency (Chen and Holden, 2016). The GHG emission from enteric fermentation also account for a big part of the total GHG emission of milk production. However, this emission depends on biological characteristics of cattle and it is hard to improve through farm management. Dairy farm production consumes great amount of freshwater, more efficient water management can reduce the working time and non-fatal accident rate in upstream of the milk production chain. The best possible options for improving the environmental impacts of dairy and beef farm are feed composition, fertilizer application and manure management.

The hotspots identified in this study in the VALUMICS confirm the results from previous studies. For the salmon supply chain, feed was the main environmental hotspot in different salmon production systems in world (Ziegler et al., 2016, Pelletier et al., 2009). The composition of salmon feed can greatly influence the emission intensity of salmon

feed. Ziegler et al. (2013) also found that air transport in salmon supply chain accounts a significant share of GHG emission. The GHG emission of airfreight to Tokyo is almost 3.8 times the GHG emission from aquaculture, which is greater than the result in this study (2.4 times). The main reason for this difference is the greater GHG emission per kg of salmon feed used and the shorter transport distance in this study. In butter and beef supply chains, previous studies found primary production on farm is the main contributor to most of impacts (Flysjö, 2011, Flysjö et al., 2014, Wiedemann et al., 2015, de Vries et al., 2015). The impacts of farm production and total supply chain impacts in this study are within the range of impact values in previous studies. The enteric fermentation is the main contributor to GHG emission in both dairy and beef farms. In this study, the share of enteric fermentation in beef farm (57%) is more significant than the previous studies (around 50%) (Foley et al., 2011). The lower beef productivity and higher feed consumption is the main reason for this difference. For GHG emission on dairy farm, the share of enteric fermentation in this study (42%) is close to previous findings (45%). The shares of GHG emission from other processes in farm follow the similar trends in previous findings (O'Brien et al., 2012).

4.2 FUTURE SCENARIOS FOR FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS

Feed was identified as one of the main aspects that can be managed to improve the sustainability performance in salmon, butter and beef supply chains. Currently, there are also many research projects and commercial applications in promoting alternative feed ingredients. Among those alternatives, most options were developed to save energy and cost, and ingredients were normally from conventional feed crop or vegetation (Yan et al., 2013a, Yorks et al., 1980). In addition, insect and microalgae protein was also used as innovative alternatives for feed ingredients (Donkin et al., 2003, Kiron et al., 2012, Belghit et al., 2018). These innovative feed ingredients potentially provide great environmental benefits, especially on climate change. Rustad (2016) found the GHG emission per kg salmon meal produced from the black soldier fly was 0.5 kg (including indirect impacts), which is only around 20% of GHG intensity of salmon feed used in this study. For cattle farming system, insect and microalgae derived protein is still used as feed supplement, not to replace feed in a significant way

(Taelman et al., 2015, Donkin et al., 2003). Although the new feed ingredients may have much better environmental performance, the impacts on entire supply chains have not been comprehensively investigated. There are some uncertainties in the production performance. For example, whether the new feed will affect the growth of salmon, including the death rate of fish. In the dairy system, it is also not clear that whether the new feed has any effect on milk quality, especially the fat and protein content in raw milk. These production parameters can influence the environmental and social impacts of food supply chain. Therefore, more production data is required to evaluate the real impacts of innovative feed in food supply chains.

According to Springmann et al. (2018a), dietary changes could bring significant effect on environmental impacts of global food supply chains. However, there are also uncertainties in the changes of global food demand, especially the regional demand for fish and meat. In high-income countries, Springmann et al. (2018b) found a trend of replacing animal-source food with plant-based ones to improve nutrient level and have a healthier diet. Among European countries, the individual meat consumption is projected to decrease from 2010 to 2020, while the demand of salmon keeps increasing (Statista). However, the resolution of projected demands in these studies still needs to be improved. There is no detailed estimation of particular type of food in specific country. For the meat demand, although there is a trend of replacing meat with fish in developed countries. From global perspective, the rapidly increasing meat demand from developing countries may not only affect the local food industries, but also the meat producers in developed countries, for instance, the Irish beef producer in this study. Therefore, a detailed projection for global and regional food demand is required for future scenarios of dietary changes. In addition, to investigate the effect of dietary changes on sustainability performance of food supply chain, it is necessary to understand whether the material and energy inputs, infrastructure facility and emission will linearly change with projected outputs. The changes of input use efficiency and food productivity are the key elements for sustainability of food supply chains.

The evolution of food waste at consumption, processing and distribution losses is also an important future scenario for sustainability improvement. Based on the results in this study, the food waste and loss accounts at least 1%-13% of environmental and social impacts of entire food supply chains. It is found that there is not enough detailed

information for particular types of food waste, especially in household consumption. More comprehensive food waste database needs to be developed to evaluate the effect of food waste on specific food supply chain.

The energy system within food supply chains could also be an improvement option in the future. Currently, most of the fuel and electricity in food supply chains is derived from fossil fuels. Replacing diesel with biofuel and using electricity from renewable source can effectively reduce the environmental and social impacts of food supply chains, especially for the supply chains that use air freight. Sustainable aviation fuel can save up to 80% of GHG emission of conventional aviation fuel (Pierobon et al., 2018, de Jong et al., 2017). In addition, sustainable biofuel also has potential to improve the social impact of aviation fuel supply chain (Wang et al., 2018). Apart from the energy system in air transport, substituting the air transport with sea or on-road transport also contributes to improve sustainability of food supply chain. If the transport time is not considered, the main issue for sea or on-road transport system is how to keep food as much fresh as possible. For some food products, frozen food may have less favourable position in market. Therefore, a better cold chain system for sea or on-road transport need to be designed. According to a pilot study by DNV-GL in 2018, by replacing 30% of the current volume of transport by road to sea will reduce carbon emissions from transport of fresh salmon from Norway to the continent by 70%. The sea route suggested by the study takes up to 2 days more than the land route and therefore a new refrigeration technology called super chilling is suggested to extend the shelf life of the fish during sea transport. The scenarios analysed in the study also show that the cost of transporting fish by sea will be reduced by 20-30% due to the reduced costs of conventional chilling of fish.

For cattle farming system, better manure management (especially in housing stage) and fertilizer application can also effectively contribute to reduce the GHG emission and eutrophication of food supply chain. These two processes are responsible for considerable emission of NH_3 , N_2O , CH_4 and nitrate leaching on farm. In order to assess the sustainability improvement of better manure management and fertilizer application, more data about change of operation and extra inputs and equipment is required.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This LCA and Social-LCA report adopted a holistic approach to evaluate the environmental and social impacts of selected case studies. The system boundary covers entire food supply chain, including raw materials extraction, primary production on farm, food processing, distribution and retail, and consumption stages. For each food case study, different distribution networks and end markets are defined. The environmental and social hotspots in each food supply chains were identified. The results suggested primary production on farm is the main environmental and social hotspots in salmon, butter and beef supply chains. The air transport could also have significant effect on total impact of selected food supply chains. In farm production, different hotspots were identified in each type of food production system. Feed production and consumption is the general hotspot in all types of farm production. It has significant impact on climate change. In addition to feed, on-farm operation is also an important contributor to many impact indicators, especially social indicators. In cattle farming system, the fertilizer application, manure management system and animal enteric fermentation also greatly influence many environmental indicators, e.g. climate change, eutrophication and acidification. Food waste was also identified as an important driver of impact, which varies by market and product type. Across the case study systems modelled, novel feed ingredients, sustainable aviation fuel and reduction of wasted food can effectively reduce the GHG emission (and other impacts), and the combined approach with three options could decrease GHG emission by 15% to 82% depending on raw material, product type, market and transport. These externalities are not currently priced in the market for these materials and products and have little impact on consumer choice compared to type of product (e.g. meat vs vegetable). The future potential to improve the environmental and social sustainability performance of selected food supply chains has been identified in this task. However, due to the data unavailability, the comprehensive sustainability impacts of food supply chains in these scenarios were not evaluated by LCA. In order to investigate the sustainability impacts of food supply chain for these future scenarios, more data collection is required for the on-farm production processes, food processing, distribution and consumption stages.

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7. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. Impacts contribution of main stages in Norwegian salmon supply chain in Norway

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.34E-05	1.34E-06	6.03E-08	2.11E-07	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	3.19E+01	3.19E+00	1.43E-01	7.93E-01	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.04E+01	1.04E+00	4.67E-02	5.45E-02	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.71E-07	2.71E-08	1.22E-09	1.14E-08	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.06E+00	1.06E-01	4.76E-03	1.50E-02	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.07E+00	1.07E-01	4.83E-03	1.16E-02	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.19E+03	2.19E+02	9.86E+00	2.24E+01	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.80E-01	1.80E-02	8.12E-04	6.50E-05	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1.98E-03	1.98E-04	8.90E-06	7.93E-06	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	4.82E-02	4.82E-03	2.17E-04	1.24E-04	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	5.84E-02	5.84E-03	2.63E-04	2.80E-05	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.13E+02	5.13E+01	2.31E+00	9.14E-01	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	3.65E-06	3.65E-07	1.64E-08	2.58E-09	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	2.01E-08	2.01E-09	9.06E-11	1.77E-12	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 2. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish butter supply chain to Germany

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (ship)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.37E-05	1.10E-06	6.32E-08	6.82E-07	1.05E-07	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	3.36E+01	2.69E+00	1.54E-01	2.57E+00	4.25E-01	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.03E+01	8.25E-01	4.74E-02	1.77E-01	2.93E-02	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.98E-07	2.38E-08	1.37E-09	3.68E-08	4.98E-09	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.08E+00	8.64E-02	4.97E-03	4.87E-02	8.29E-03	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.08E+00	8.66E-02	4.98E-03	3.75E-02	4.04E-03	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.22E+03	1.77E+02	1.02E+01	7.25E+01	1.72E+01	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.77E-01	1.41E-02	8.13E-04	2.10E-04	3.63E-05	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1.97E-03	1.58E-04	9.06E-06	2.57E-05	1.49E-05	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	4.80E-02	3.84E-03	2.21E-04	4.03E-04	4.49E-04	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	5.72E-02	4.58E-03	2.63E-04	9.08E-05	6.43E-05	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.04E+02	4.03E+01	2.32E+00	2.96E+00	2.92E-01	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	3.58E-06	2.86E-07	1.65E-08	8.36E-09	3.30E-09	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	1.97E-08	1.58E-09	9.06E-11	5.73E-12	2.20E-12	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 3. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish butter supply chain to Japan

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (plane)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.33E-05	1.33E-07	6.59E-08	2.11E-07	1.10E-06	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	1.95E+02	1.95E+00	9.63E-01	7.93E-01	1.63E+02	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	2.03E+01	2.03E-01	1.00E-01	5.45E-02	1.07E+01	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.23E-06	2.23E-08	1.11E-08	1.14E-08	1.96E-06	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.27E+00	9.27E-02	4.59E-02	1.50E-02	8.18E+00	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.25E+00	1.25E-02	6.18E-03	1.16E-02	2.69E-01	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.08E+03	3.08E+01	1.52E+01	2.24E+01	1.07E+03	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.67E-01	1.67E-03	8.29E-04	6.50E-05	3.46E-03	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	3.54E-03	3.54E-05	1.75E-05	7.93E-06	1.71E-03	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	8.46E-02	8.46E-04	4.19E-04	1.24E-04	4.02E-02	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	6.06E-02	6.06E-04	3.00E-04	2.80E-05	7.47E-03	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.70E+02	5.70E+00	2.82E+00	9.14E-01	1.03E+02	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	4.48E-06	4.48E-08	2.22E-08	2.58E-09	1.15E-06	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	1.91E-08	1.91E-10	9.44E-11	1.77E-12	7.69E-10	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 4. GHG emission share in salmon supply chain to China in Simapro

ANNEX 5. Butter LCA model from cradle to processing gate in Simapro

ANNEX 6. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish butter supply chain in Ireland

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.34E-05	1.34E-06	6.03E-08	2.11E-07	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	3.19E+01	3.19E+00	1.43E-01	7.93E-01	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.04E+01	1.04E+00	4.67E-02	5.45E-02	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.71E-07	2.71E-08	1.22E-09	1.14E-08	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.06E+00	1.06E-01	4.76E-03	1.50E-02	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.07E+00	1.07E-01	4.83E-03	1.16E-02	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.19E+03	2.19E+02	9.86E+00	2.24E+01	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.80E-01	1.80E-02	8.12E-04	6.50E-05	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1.98E-03	1.98E-04	8.90E-06	7.93E-06	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	4.82E-02	4.82E-03	2.17E-04	1.24E-04	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	5.84E-02	5.84E-03	2.63E-04	2.80E-05	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.13E+02	5.13E+01	2.31E+00	9.14E-01	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	3.65E-06	3.65E-07	1.64E-08	2.58E-09	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	2.01E-08	2.01E-09	9.06E-11	1.77E-12	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 7. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish butter supply chain to Germany

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (ship)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.37E-05	1.10E-06	6.32E-08	6.82E-07	1.05E-07	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	3.36E+01	2.69E+00	1.54E-01	2.57E+00	4.25E-01	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.03E+01	8.25E-01	4.74E-02	1.77E-01	2.93E-02	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.98E-07	2.38E-08	1.37E-09	3.68E-08	4.98E-09	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.08E+00	8.64E-02	4.97E-03	4.87E-02	8.29E-03	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.08E+00	8.66E-02	4.98E-03	3.75E-02	4.04E-03	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.22E+03	1.77E+02	1.02E+01	7.25E+01	1.72E+01	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.77E-01	1.41E-02	8.13E-04	2.10E-04	3.63E-05	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1.97E-03	1.58E-04	9.06E-06	2.57E-05	1.49E-05	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	4.80E-02	3.84E-03	2.21E-04	4.03E-04	4.49E-04	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	5.72E-02	4.58E-03	2.63E-04	9.08E-05	6.43E-05	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.04E+02	4.03E+01	2.32E+00	2.96E+00	2.92E-01	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	3.58E-06	2.86E-07	1.65E-08	8.36E-09	3.30E-09	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	1.97E-08	1.58E-09	9.06E-11	5.73E-12	2.20E-12	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 8. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish butter supply chain to Japan

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (plane)	Processing	Raw milk
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.33E-05	1.33E-07	6.59E-08	2.11E-07	1.10E-06	1.00E-06	1.08E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	1.95E+02	1.95E+00	9.63E-01	7.93E-01	1.63E+02	4.38E+00	2.34E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	2.03E+01	2.03E-01	1.00E-01	5.45E-02	1.07E+01	3.93E-01	8.84E+00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.23E-06	2.23E-08	1.11E-08	1.14E-08	1.96E-06	1.61E-08	2.15E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.27E+00	9.27E-02	4.59E-02	1.50E-02	8.18E+00	7.75E-02	8.55E-01
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.25E+00	1.25E-02	6.18E-03	1.16E-02	2.69E-01	1.55E-01	7.95E-01
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.08E+03	3.08E+01	1.52E+01	2.24E+01	1.07E+03	4.53E+02	1.49E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.67E-01	1.67E-03	8.29E-04	6.50E-05	3.46E-03	7.93E-04	1.61E-01
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	3.54E-03	3.54E-05	1.75E-05	7.93E-06	1.71E-03	7.13E-05	1.69E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	8.46E-02	8.46E-04	4.19E-04	1.24E-04	4.02E-02	1.26E-03	4.18E-02
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	6.06E-02	6.06E-04	3.00E-04	2.80E-05	7.47E-03	4.26E-04	5.18E-02
Working time	s	5.70E+02	5.70E+00	2.82E+00	9.14E-01	1.03E+02	7.51E+01	3.82E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	4.48E-06	4.48E-08	2.22E-08	2.58E-09	1.15E-06	6.68E-07	2.60E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	1.91E-08	1.91E-10	9.44E-11	1.77E-12	7.69E-10	7.49E-10	1.73E-08

ANNEX 9. GHG emission share in butter supply chain to Japan in Simapro

ANNEX 10. LCA model for beef production in Simapro

ANNEX 11. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish beef supply chain in Ireland

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Processing	Beef farming
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	3.35E-05	2.01E-06	7.86E-07	2.66E-07	0.00E+00	4.77E-08
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	6.16E+01	3.70E+00	1.45E+00	1.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.43E+00
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.96E+01	1.17E+00	4.60E-01	6.90E-02	0.00E+00	1.32E-01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	5.45E-07	3.27E-08	1.28E-08	1.44E-08	0.00E+00	1.89E-09
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.06E+00	1.24E-01	4.84E-02	1.90E-02	0.00E+00	1.48E-02
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.26E+00	7.55E-02	2.96E-02	1.47E-02	0.00E+00	8.24E-03
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.51E+03	2.71E+02	1.06E+02	2.83E+01	0.00E+00	1.03E+02
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.71E-02	5.82E-03	2.28E-03	8.22E-05	0.00E+00	1.18E-04
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	3.76E-03	2.26E-04	8.84E-05	1.00E-05	0.00E+00	3.52E-05
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	1.22E-01	7.34E-03	2.87E-03	1.57E-04	0.00E+00	7.34E-04
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	1.06E-01	6.34E-03	2.49E-03	3.55E-05	0.00E+00	8.24E-05
Working time	s	5.40E+02	3.24E+01	1.27E+01	1.16E+00	0.00E+00	6.94E+00
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	1.48E-06	8.87E-08	3.48E-08	3.26E-09	0.00E+00	9.04E-08
Injuries, fatal	case	3.83E-09	2.30E-10	9.01E-11	2.24E-12	0.00E+00	1.77E-12

ANNEX 12. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish beef supply chain to UK

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (ship)	Processing	Beef farming
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	3.37E-05	2.02E-06	7.92E-07	4.28E-07	4.88E-08	4.77E-08	3.04E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	6.25E+01	3.75E+00	1.47E+00	1.61E+00	1.98E-01	1.43E+00	5.41E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	1.96E+01	1.18E+00	4.61E-01	1.11E-01	1.36E-02	1.32E-01	1.77E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	5.58E-07	3.35E-08	1.31E-08	2.31E-08	2.32E-09	1.89E-09	4.84E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.08E+00	1.25E-01	4.88E-02	3.06E-02	3.86E-03	1.48E-02	1.86E+00
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.27E+00	7.62E-02	2.99E-02	2.36E-02	1.88E-03	8.24E-03	1.13E+00
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.54E+03	2.72E+02	1.07E+02	4.55E+01	8.01E+00	1.03E+02	4.00E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.71E-02	5.83E-03	2.28E-03	1.32E-04	1.69E-05	1.18E-04	8.88E-02
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	3.78E-03	2.27E-04	8.87E-05	1.61E-05	6.92E-06	3.52E-05	3.40E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	1.23E-01	7.36E-03	2.88E-03	2.53E-04	2.09E-04	7.34E-04	1.11E-01
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	1.06E-01	6.35E-03	2.49E-03	5.71E-05	2.99E-05	8.24E-05	9.68E-02
Working time	s	5.41E+02	3.25E+01	1.27E+01	1.86E+00	1.36E-01	6.94E+00	4.87E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	1.48E-06	8.90E-08	3.48E-08	5.25E-09	1.53E-09	9.04E-08	1.26E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	3.83E-09	2.30E-10	9.01E-11	3.60E-12	1.02E-12	1.77E-12	3.51E-09

ANNEX 13. Impacts contribution of main stages in Irish beef supply chain to USA

Impact category	Unit	Total	Consumer waste	Retail	Transport (truck)	Transport (plane)	Processing	Beef farming
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	3.66E-05	4.76E-06	7.96E-07	6.63E-08	5.65E-07	4.77E-08	3.04E-05
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	1.64E+02	2.13E+01	3.57E+00	2.50E-01	8.35E+01	1.43E+00	5.41E+01
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	2.75E+01	3.58E+00	5.99E-01	1.72E-02	5.46E+00	1.32E-01	1.77E+01
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	1.76E-06	2.28E-07	3.82E-08	3.58E-09	1.00E-06	1.89E-09	4.84E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	7.14E+00	9.29E-01	1.55E-01	4.73E-03	4.18E+00	1.48E-02	1.86E+00
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.51E+00	1.96E-01	3.28E-02	3.65E-03	1.38E-01	8.24E-03	1.13E+00
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.49E+03	7.14E+02	1.19E+02	7.05E+00	5.48E+02	1.03E+02	4.00E+03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.07E-01	1.39E-02	2.32E-03	2.05E-05	1.77E-03	1.18E-04	8.88E-02
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	5.09E-03	6.61E-04	1.11E-04	2.50E-06	8.76E-04	3.52E-05	3.40E-03
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	1.56E-01	2.03E-02	3.40E-03	3.91E-05	2.05E-02	7.34E-04	1.11E-01
Eutrophication	kg PO4 ⁻⁻⁻ eq	1.19E-01	1.54E-02	2.58E-03	8.83E-06	3.82E-03	8.24E-05	9.68E-02
Working time	s	6.44E+02	8.38E+01	1.40E+01	2.88E-01	5.25E+01	6.94E+00	4.87E+02
Injuries, non-fatal, at work	case	2.29E-06	2.98E-07	4.98E-08	8.13E-10	5.88E-07	9.04E-08	1.26E-06
Injuries, fatal	case	4.60E-09	5.98E-10	1.00E-10	5.58E-13	3.93E-10	1.77E-12	3.51E-09

ANNEX 14. GHG emission share in beef supply chain to USA in Simapro

